

Statement of participation

Srignana Lokesh Ezhil

has completed the free course including any mandatory tests for:

Digital innovation in social care and social work

This free 4-hour course explored how digital innovation has made a difference to social care and social work.

Issue date: 2 November 2025

www.open.edu/openlearn

This statement does not imply the award of credit points nor the conferment of a University Qualification.
This statement confirms that this free course and all mandatory tests were passed by the learner.

Please go to the course on OpenLearn for full details:

<https://www.open.edu/openlearn/health-sports-psychology/digital-innovation-social-care-and-social-work/content-section-0>

COURSE CODE: K102_5

Digital innovation in social care and social work

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Course summary

This free course, Digital innovation in social care and social work, explores how digital technology has made a difference, both to the social care sector and people living in their own communities. You will also learn about how incorporating technology in the home and in community settings has a range of benefits to people's wellbeing and ability to maintain independence in their community setting.

Learning outcomes

By completing this course, the learner should be able to:

- identify the ways in which digital technologies are used in social care services
- evaluate the impact of digital technologies in the home and community on peoples' wellbeing
- evaluate how digital technologies in social care can impact on the cost and sustainability of service provision.

Completed study

The learner has completed the following:

Section 1

Digital technology and social care

Section 2

Digital and technology strategies in the UK

Section 3

Smart tech and home care

Section 4

Technology-enhanced care in Wales

Section 5

Supporting young people

Section 6

Barriers to transforming care